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EVALUATION OF CARDIAC SPECIFIC MARKER CARDIAC TROPONIN I AFTER CORONARY BYPASS SURGERY.

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Abstract

Background: Cardiac troponin I (cTnI) is reported to be very specific for myocardial cell damage without cross reactivity with skeletal muscle isoform. Evaluation of cTnI after CABG will be useful as an early marker of excessive post-operative myocardial damage when a specific therapeutic intervention can still be efficient and improve outcome.

Methodology: The study comprised of 50 patients who undergo Coronary artery bypass surgery at V.S group of Hospital. Blood samples were taken after 12 hours (T12) and 24 hours (T24) of post-CABG. The samples were analysed for cTnI.

Results: Our results show that Troponin I levels after 2 hours, 12 hours and 24 hours in patients who had better outcome after CABG was 9.2 ng/ml, 13.9 ng/ml and 10.9 ng/ml respectively.

Whereas, Troponin I levels after 2 hours, 12 hours and 24 hours in patients who had adverse outcome like death of patients after CABG was 10.6 ng/ml, 38.7 ng/ml and 28.9 ng/ml respectively.

Conclusion: Routine measurement of cardiac troponin levels after cardiac troponin can identify a group of patients at increased risk of complications or death.

Key words: Cardiac Troponin I (cTnI), Coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG), Post-operative myocardial infarction (PMI).

Introduction

There are mainly three different forms of troponin associated with contractile myofibril proteins: TnC (calcium binding molecular mass 18 kDa), TnI (inhibitory component molecular mass 22.5 kDa), TnT (tropomyosin-binding component molecular mass 37 kDa) which are mainly in muscle and minor fraction in cytosol.¹

However cardiac specific isoforms (cTnI, cTnT) are identified from multiple troponin isoforms in muscle and measured. cTnI and cTnT are released in response to myocardial injury due to any cause. In acute myocardial ischemia cTn measured in peripheral blood within 4 hours; with new high sensitive cTn (hsTn) we can detect earlier than 4 hours. Concentration of cTn depends on size of infarct within 24-48 hours and remain high for period of days.

Cardiac troponin I (cTnI) is reported to be very specific for myocardial cell damage without cross reactivity with skeletal muscle isoform (1). The specificity cardiac troponin I has been confirmed in various situations like myocardial infarction, contusion, myocarditis and renal failure. In general, for confirmation of diagnosis of myocardial infarction by measuring cardiac troponin in patient having symptoms and clinical signs suggestive of myocardial ischemia.²

Hence measurement of cardiac troponin in patients helpful for early diagnosis and decrease

recurrence of myocardial infarction and adverse outcome like death etc. in patients having suspected myocardial infarction. (3,4)

There are many methods exist for to identify risk early like EUROSCORE, Biomarkers measurement (natriuretic peptides, creatine kinase (CK), or the cardiac troponins (cTn), myoglobin) for complication after cardiac surgical procedures. so we can easily predict prognosis for adverse outcome may helpful in early therapeutic interventions following surgery like coronary artery bypass graft CABG. However, all biomarkers have been shown to predict risks but have limited use due to exact mechanism of release not well explain during and after operations. cardiac troponin measurement is superior than CK MB isoenzyme for risk prediction in post-operative cardiac surgery due to more specificity. (5,6,7,8)

As cardiac troponin I measurement is objective, superior than subjective for assessment of underlying pathology of patients in myocardial necrosis commonly used “gold standard “ for diagnosis and predictions of risk in cardiovascular disease.²

cTn may increased after cardiac surgery due to multiple reasons like cardiac manipulation, hemodynamic instability, injury, intra operative defibrillation, acute loss of grafts.⁹

Evaluation of cTnI after CABG will be useful as an early marker of excessive post-operative myocardial damage when a specific therapeutic intervention can still be efficient and improve outcome.

Ischemic heart disease is highly prevalent in residents of the Ahmedabad. Many patients undergo coronary artery bypass surgery (CABG) in the city as a routine. No systemic database study of the cardiac specific marker Cardiac Troponin I after CABG has been done in Ahmedabad population considering ethnic diversity of the city.

Methodology

The study comprised of retrospective analysis 50 patient's registry who undergone Coronary artery bypass surgery (CABG) at V.S group of Hospital between 2014 Dec to Dec 2016.

Inclusion criteria were reports of patients undergone CABG.

Blood sample were taken after 2 hours, 12 hour (T12) and 24 hour (T24) of post CABG. The sample were analysed for cTnI. The outcome measured with major adverse cardiac events like death, myocardial infarction, thrombosis etc...

The blood samples were collected in vials containing no anticoagulant or preservative. The samples were collected using a disposable needle and syringe and care was taken to get non hemolysed samples. The serum samples were analyzed for cTnI with well standardized method. The serum cTnI concentration was measured using the reagent kit manufactured by Abott c8000 architect system using CMIA (Chemiluminescent micro particle immunoassay).

Results:

Out of 50 patients post CABG, Group 1 comprised of 35 patients who had better outcomes, while 15 patients had adverse outcome in the form of adverse cardiac events like death of patient.

Normal reference value of Troponin I in healthy people is <0.04 ng/dl. For troponin concentrations 0.40 ng/mL and higher, maybe suggestive of the underlying cardiac injury. Our results show that Troponin I levels after 2 hours, 12 hours and 24 hours in patients who had better outcome after CABG was 9.2 ng/ml, 13.9 ng/ml and 10.9 ng/ml respectively (Table 1).

Whereas, Troponin I levels after 2 hours, 12 hours and 24 hours in patients who had adverse outcome like death of patients after CABG was 10.6 ng/ml, 38.7 ng/ml and 28.9 ng/ml respectively (Table 1).

Table 1: Troponin I levels post CABG.

	Troponin I (ng/ml) After 2 hours (Interquarantilerange)	Troponin I (ng/ml) After 12 hours (Interquarantilerange)	Troponin I (ng/ml) After 24 hours (Interquarantile range)
Group 1 (n=35)	9.2 (1.4-17.5)	13.9 (8.5-15.5)	10.9 (5.7-15.1)
Group 2 (n=15)	10.6 (10.6-25.7)	38.7 (28.8-63.8)	28.9 (22.8-61)

Discussion:

Our study comprised of measurement of cTnI in patients undergone coronary artery bypass study after 12 hour (T12) and 24 hour (T24) of post CABG.

Troponin I is a regulatory subunit of the troponin complex associated with the actin filament within muscle cell. Clinical studies have demonstrated the release of troponin I into the blood stream within hours following AMI or ischemic damage.

The measurements of serum enzymes as a reflection of damage to myocardial muscle cells still play an important role in the diagnosis of AMI. Our results show that troponin I level was elevated at 2 hours, 12 hours and 24 hours after coronary bypass surgery. However, it was seen that 15 patients out of 50 developed post operative complications. Troponin I level in these 15 patients remained high even after 24 hours of surgery compared to group 1 patients who did not develop complications.

Cardiac surgery may be associated with significant perioperative and postoperative morbidity and mortality. Intraoperative injury may be due to cardiac manipulation, defibrillation, acute post bypass hemodynamic instability. These can cause elevation of cardiac markers.

Cardiac troponins have shown to be specific markers of myocardial injury. cTnI is more cardiac specific than other cardiac markers like CK-MB and can be used as a tool for diagnosis of myocardial infarction after cardiac surgery. cTnI could be a marker of myocardial ischemia after open heart surgery.¹⁰

The National Academy of Clinical Biochemistry issued a guideline in 2007 that stated that "in the presence of a clinical history suggestive of Acute cardiac syndrome, the following is considered indicative of myocardial necrosis consistent with myocardial infarction: maximal concentration of cTn exceeding the 99th percentile of values."¹¹

In our study, cardiac Troponin I was found to be low in patients who had undergone CABG surgery, having no adverse effects post CABG. Study by¹² had similar findings, serum levels of cardiac troponin remained low after uncomplicated CABG. Low levels of cTnI within 24 to 48 hours after cardiac surgery is suggestive of absence of perioperative myocardial necrosis.¹³

In our study, cardiac Troponin I was found to be high in patients who had undergone CABG surgery, having adverse cardiac complications / effects post CABG. In this group of patients, cTnI was not elevated 2 hours after CABG, but after 12 hours, the increase was more pronounced. Changes in cTnI levels immediately after surgery may not be very useful in predicting outcomes as the changes may be due to surgery itself. cTnI levels 24 hours after

surgery are more powerful short as well as long term predictors of mortality rather than after 2 hours .¹⁴ cTnI levels at 24 hours can be used to predict short-, medium- and long-term outcome in cardiac surgery patients.

Conclusion:

Troponin I levels post cardiac surgery can be used to identify patients at risk of developing complications or adverse cardiac reactions. Identification of such patients, in early stage, can help in improving the outcome as well as reducing morbidity and mortality.

Cardiac troponin I levels are frequently elevated after cardiac surgery. However, cardiac troponin levels measured 24 hours after surgery were independently predictive of complications post operatively after CABG. These data suggest that routine measurement of cardiac troponin levels after cardiac troponin can identify group of patients at increased risk of complications or death.

References:

- 1) Parmacek MS, Solaro RJ. Biology of the troponin complex in cardiac myocytes. *Prog Cardiovasc DisM.* 2004;47:159–176. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 2) Thygesen K, Alpert JS, Jaffe AS, Simoons ML, Chaitman BR, White HD, et al. Third universal definition of myocardial infarction. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 2012;60:1581–98.)
- 3) Mills NL, Churchhouse AM, Lee KK, et al. Implementation of a sensitivetroponin I assay and risk of recurrent myocardial infarction and death in patients with suspected acute coronary syndrome. *JAMA* 2011;305:1210–6.
- 4) Mills NL, Lee KK, McAllister DA, Anand A, Gamble D, Shah AS, et al. Implications of lowering threshold of plasma troponin concentration indagnosis of myocardial infarction: cohort study. *BMJ* 2012;344:e1533.
- 5) Bignami E, Landoni G, Crescenzi G. et al. Role of cardiac biomarkers (troponin I and CK-MB)as predictors of quality of life and long-term outcome after cardiac surgery. *Ann Card Anaesth.* 2009;12:22–26. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 6) Januzzi JL, Lewandrowski K, MacGillivray TE. et al. A comparison of cardiac troponin T andcreatine kinase-MB for patient evaluation after cardiac surgery. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2002;39:1518–1523. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 7) Thielmann M, Massoudy P, Marggraf G. et al. Role of troponin I, myoglobin, and creatine kinase for the detection of early graft failure following coronary artery bypass grafting. *Eur JCardiothorac Surg.* 2004;26:102–109. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 8) Tzimas PG, Milionis HJ, Arnaoutoglou HM. et al. Cardiac troponin I versus creatine kinase-MB in the detection of postoperative cardiac events after coronary artery bypass grafting surgery. *J Cardiovasc Surg.* 2008;49:95–101. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 9) Mohammed AA, Agnihotri AK, van Kimmenade RR. et al. Prospective, ComprehensiveAssessment of Cardiac Troponin T Testing Following Coronary Artery Bypass Graft Surgery. *Circulation.* 2009 [[Epub ahead of print.](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 10). Peivandi AA, Dahm M, Opfermann UT, Peetz D, Doerr F, Loos A, Oelert H. Comparison of cardiac troponin I versus T and creatine kinase MB after coronary artery bypass grafting in patients with and without perioperative myocardial infarction. *Herz.* 2004 Nov;29(7):658-64.
- 11). Vermes E, Mesguich M, Houel R, Soustelle C, Le Besnerais P, Hillion ML, Loisançe D. Cardiac troponin I release after open heart surgery: a marker of myocardial protection? *Ann Thorac Surg.* 2000 Dec;70(6):2087-90.
- 12). Alyanakian MA, Dehoux M, Chatel D, Seguret C, Desmonts JM, Durand G, Philip I.

Cardiac troponin I in diagnosis of perioperative myocardial infarction after cardiac surgery. *J Cardiothorac Vasc Anesth.* 1998 Jun;12(3):288-94.

13). Bernard L. Croal, Graham S. Hillis, Patrick H. Gibson, Mohammed T. Fazal, Hussein El- Shafei, George Gibson, Robert R. Jeffrey, Keith G. Buchan, Douglas West, Brian H. Cuthbertson. Relationship Between Postoperative Cardiac Troponin I Levels and Outcome of Cardiac Surgery. *Circulation.* 2006;114:1468–1475.

14). Vinay S Mahajan, Petr Jarolim. How to interpret elevated cardiac troponin levels. *Circulation.* 2011;124:2350–2354.

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